

Challenges of ChatGPT for Mathematics Learning and Teaching

Anthony E. Kelly¹ and Barry Sloane²

¹George Mason University, ²U S National Science Foundation

We discuss ChatGPT (OpenAI, 2022), and its potential uses in mathematics education. ChatGPT can process and respond to natural language inputs with outputs that are human-like. It can output translations, text generation, conversations, and question answering, write code, perform statistical analysis as well as write exam items and answers, poems, and short stories (Topsakal & Topsakal, 2022; Zhai, 2023). Yet, it confidently “hallucinates” responses, often with made up “facts” and fabricated references. It also can repeat and mimic human falsehoods and other misinformation from its database (Lin et al., 2022). Critically, ChatGPT may generate text records that are offensive, sexist, racist or that teach immoral perspectives (Krügel et al., 2023). Its performance on certain standardized tests is impressive. For use in K-12 science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) education, however, low accuracy for STEM content was found for GPT-3 over 57 tasks (e.g., mathematics, high school and undergraduate topics like computer science, high school biology, and other areas such as moral disputes, and econometrics) (Hendrycks et al., 2022). How should K-12 mathematics educators understand ChatGPT: a tool that produces – unpredictably and without assessments of quality– (a) dependable, (b) questionable, or (c) false and toxic output, or these in combination?

Keywords: ChatGPT, mathematics learning, teaching

Chatbots and ChatGPT

AI and other chatbots are based on large language models (LLMs), a technology that is trained on massive amounts of text from the internet. Chatbots have been used with teachers in language education (Ji et al., 2023), including chatbots for teacher education, yet rarely used in mathematics education (Belda-Medina et al., 2022). Indeed, in the very recent past, LLMs were available only to skilled researchers (e.g., Rae et al., 2022). However, on November 30, 2022, the company OpenAI released to the public an easy-to-use chatbot for GPT-3, called ChatGPT (OpenAI, 2022). For a comprehensive review of the development of ChatGPT from GPT-3, see Lovegrove (n.d.) and Kasneci et al. (2023).

The uptake of ChatGPT, globally, is phenomenal. By January 2023, 100 million downloads of ChatGPT had occurred. Since its release, ChatGPT has evolved to ChatGPTPlus, which had more features than the free version. In March, 15, 2023, OpenAI released the latest version of their LLM (GPT-4), which now is the model underlying ChatGPT-Plus (OpenAI, 2023a).

ChatGPT can process and respond to natural language inputs with outputs that are human-like. It can output translations, text generation, conversations, and question answering, write code, and perform statistical analysis as well as write exam items and answers, poems, and short stories (Topsakal & Topsakal, 2022; Zhai, 2023). Some predict that ChatGPT will soon “design experiments, write and complete manuscripts, conduct peer review and support editorial decisions to accept or reject manuscripts” (van Dis et al., 2023, p. 224).

ChatGPT: A Disruptive Chatbot

ChatGPT is a double-edged tool, however. The LLM on which ChatGPT is trained is proprietary, so its shortcomings and biases are difficult to document (Brundage et al., 2018; van Dis et al., 2023). For those wishing to understand what may be happening in the ChatGPT black box, see an analysis of the behavior of open LLM such as LLaMA (Touvron et al., n.d.).

Since the GPT models are trained on the internet, there are significant biases and other flaws in the LLM. Detoxifying LLM is a challenging task. First, humans have to review and reject deeply offensive output. The subsequent stage of “fine-tuning” the chatbot requires reinforcement learning with human feedback (RLHF). During RLHF, the machine “learns” what type of output is rewarded by human training. RLHF may itself introduce additional errors given the cognitive biases and limitations of the trainers (Azaria, n.d; Tabassi, 2023). For papers on RLHF and a range of topics from misinformation, AI value-alignment, bias, immorality, and cross-cultural dialogue, see Glaese et al. (2022). OpenAI (2023b) remains openly concerned about its chatbot’s toxic nature and uses.

Most importantly, because the LLM has no “model of the world” (Hendrycks et al. 2022), it may display falsehoods in addition to toxic output. ChatGPT may draw on and generate untruthful, non-representative or biased information, write false reports, manufacture plausible sounding but fictitious concepts, and report citations that do not exist or are not germane to the argument in its reports (Cabanac et al., 2021; Lehnert, 2023; van Dis et al., 2023). A comprehensive review of ChatGPT in education may be found in Maynard (n.d.).

Teacher and Student Use of ChatGPT

In summary, ChatGPT is a tool that produces – unpredictably and without assessments of quality– (a) dependable, (b) questionable, or (c) false and toxic output, or these in combination. Despite all the concerns that have arisen about ChatGPT, across the US, the Walton Family Foundation (2023) reported use of ChatGPT by teachers and students.

When ChatGPT generates ostensibly dependable text output, the task for the student and teacher will be to establish that the output actually is reliable and trustworthy. Since ChatGPT has no comprehension filter for grade-appropriate output, the student may be unable to process this text and understand what it is communicating, leading to confusion. Unlike for a vetted textbook, the additional cost of checking ChatGPT output may be significant for the student and the teacher. If the text is accurate, and comprehensible, the student and teacher may enter into productive conversations about it. However, students and teachers will still need to worry about document provenance (e.g., plagiarism, taking credit for machine-generated text). Students need to be able to cite sources and submit only their own work (see International Baccalaureate, 2023).

However, the LLM also has “holes”: areas where it does not have adequate or authoritative text repositories on which to draw (it does not have access to data prior to 2021, and is unlikely to have had access to science articles behind paywalls). Indeed, the accuracy rates for GPT-3 on mathematics (Cobbe et al., 2021; Hendrycks, et al., 2022) and science content is low (Hendrycks et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2022). Critically, even when ChatGPT has

“insufficient information,” it confidently “hallucinates” a plausible response, often with made up “facts” and fabricated references. It also can repeat and mimic human falsehoods and other misinformation from its database (Lin et al., 2022).

When faced with misinformation, adults, even scientific reviewers (van Dis et al., 2023) and children can show exaggerated ideas about their own expertise, and may blindly trust the authority of sources due to the so-called Dunning-Kruger effect (Kruger & Dunning, 1999). A student working alone may not know that the output is scientifically suspect, including incorrect propositions, reasoning or “facts.”

The task for the student and teacher in this case is to learn how to read, understand, and to reject this text output. Importantly, the teacher and the student must not pass this information along to others or store it in a digital store where its error may be compounded. For the teacher, there is the risk of grading the student’s paper as acceptable, missing material that is “hallucinated.” Here, the teacher and student must engage in critical thinking (e.g., Ennis, 2018).

Finally, ChatGPT may generate text records that are offensive, sexist, racist or that teach immoral perspectives (Krügel et al., 2023). Some researchers believe that chatbots can be designed to be more prosocial (Ganguli et al., 2023). However, OpenAI’s moderation tools to curb offensive output for ChatGPT can be side-stepped (Hacker et al., 2023).

For toxic cases, the task for the student and teacher, and for school administration will be to establish and reinforce a STEM education milieu in which scientific integrity is upheld and societal core values such as fairness, diversity and inclusion are sustained.

Students are more likely to cheat when the risk of detection is assumed to be low. While cheating on high stakes tests is not new (Lancaster, 2020), tools like ChatGPT provide easy access, and low-cost means of violating academic standards. For complex assignments, which portion(s) are due to ChatGPT is difficult to ascertain. The problem of academic fraud not only impacts K-12 education, but continues throughout one’s career (The Economist, 2023).

Developmental Issues for Children

Children move through different developmental stages. Research is needed on how tools like ChatGPT will interact with human cognitive capabilities (Markauskaite et al., 2022). For example, what are the implications for the development of executive control, grit and other cognitive and affective states when reasoning is handed off to a tool like ChatGPT (e.g., Diamond & Ling, 2016)? New models of how children learn, preK-12, must be developed to account for the greater integration of AI into education (Poquet et al., 2021).

Some researchers have begun to examine how children self-regulate their learning with AI (Järvelä et al., 2020; Molenaar, 2022). Will an over-reliance on ChatGPT for reports and homework lead to passive and shallow learning (e.g., failing to learn arithmetic in lieu of using pocket calculators)? Or will the ease of ChatGPT-generated text output deprive a child of the need to develop persistence and grit, especially for rigorous courses that need to be taken over a number of years (e.g., Ashford et al., 2016)?

In short, the implications for K-12 mathematics education are being explored, like the AI program for teachers and students, Khanmigo (Kahn Academy, n.d.). For general users, the use of in-context prompting to get the LLM to give more useful responses has value – an approach known as “prompt engineering” (Aman’s AI Journal, n.d.). The goal of this paper is to foster critical dialogue on this new force in education.

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